

Research Article

“G-D’s Physics” New Perfected “Geulah-Directed” Universe!

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Note: *Dr. Bentovish is calling Astronomers & Cosmologists (worldwide) to carry out a further direct empirical validation of the (already validated) New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm based on a “time-sensitive” measurement of a predicted increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion – specifically during the upcoming Jewish Rosh Hashanah (JRH, New Year) two days’ time-interval due at: September 16th -17th 2023 (and onwards), relative to before the 16th-17th of September! Dr. Bentovish is now seeking one of the leading Physics Universities in the World to further assist him in this further direct validation of the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm of 21st Century Theoretical Physics. Dr. Bentovish’s e-mail is: drbentwich@gmail.com.*

Abstract

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying 20th Century’s General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT) based on the New “G-D’s Physics” proven capacity to resolve an apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between these two GRT & QM “pillars” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, and its offering of an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe (instead of the empirically “unproven” purely hypothetical “Dark-Matter” concept of the Old Paradigm); The New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm is being validated, as more valid than GRT’s & QM’s predictions, through two of its unique “Critical Predictions” regarding the “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) and “Proton-Radius Puzzle” associated findings! At the “basis” of this New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm stands the discovery of the existence of a singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe, as an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” (UF’s) computed by the UCP at the “unfathomable” rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ”! Indeed, due to the simultaneity of the UCP’s computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising every consecutive UF’s frame/s, and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe back into the UCP’s singularity “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s) the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm negated some of the key assumptions associated with the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm including: the “Big-Bang” Model, the existence of “Dark-Matter”, and “Darwin’s Natural Selection Principle” (DNSP)! Instead, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm postulates that the whole origination- sustenance- “dissolution” (“in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s) and development- of the whole physical universe has been “pre-planned” by the UCP to lead from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals, and human-beings towards the “Ultimate Geulah Goal State”, in which Humanity (and Science) recognize the singularity of this UCP as underlying (and indeed “transcending”) the physical universe and its “sublime” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, e.g., being reflected in Humanity’s Geulah State behavior!

Introduction

Twenty-First Century Theoretical Physics has undergone a major “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) to the New “G-D’s Physics” (“Computational Unified Field Theory”, CUFT) [1-47]. This “Paradigmatic-Shift” inevitably followed the appearance of a fundamental “Paradigmatic-Crisis” of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm signified by a basic “theoretical-inconsistency” between its (above-mentioned) constituting Models (e.g., GRT & QM), as well as its principle inability to explain the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., assumed to be “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, but could not be detected experimentally (despite over twenty years of intensive experimental efforts to do so)! Instead, the New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) has been shown capable of resolving this (apparent) “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM based on its discovery of a singular (higher-ordered) UCP which simultaneously computes the four basic physical features (e.g., of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and

“time”) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe – in the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ”(!) thereby producing an extremely rapid series of UF’s frames comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!

According to Thomas Kuhn’s [50], well-accepted analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions” [50], in order for science to accept such a “Paradigmatic-Shift” (in any given scientific sub-discipline), it is necessary for a few specific conditions to be fulfilled:

a) The appearance of such a “Paradigmatic-Crisis” (in that given discipline) signified by the existence of a “theoretical-inconsistency” between the “pillars” of the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm (e.g., GRT & QM, i.e., as mentioned above), as well as this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s principle inability to explain the accelerated expansion of the physical universe – e.g., assumed to “caused” by purely hypothetical “dark-matter” and “dark-energy” concepts, which are assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the matter in the universe but which could not be detected experimentally

despite numerous attempts to do so (despite twenty years of intensive experimentation)?!

b) The ability of the New (“G-D’s Physics”) Scientific paradigm to resolve this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM, as well as offer an alternative (satisfactory) theoretical explanation for the accelerated expansion of the universe: Based on “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm’s discovery of the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle’s” (UCP’s) simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for each consecutive UF’s frame/s), it has been shown that this UCP simultaneously computes all “Single Spatial-Temporal” (SST) “particle/objects”; “Multiple Spatial-Temporal” (MST) “wave-phenomena”; and “Exhaustive Spatial-Temporal” “Universal Frame/s” computations! In this manner, the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm has been shown capable of resolving the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT’s strict “Speed of Light Barrier” (SLB) as opposed to QM’s “Quantum Entanglement” phenomena’s implication wherein a certain measurement of one subatomic “entangled particle’s” (“complimentary pairs” value may “instantaneously” affect the other “entangled particle’s” complimentary (energy/mass or time/mass) value?! This is simply because according to “G-D’s Physics broader EST computation – which embeds (within it) the relatively more “constrictive” UCP’s MST and SST computations, the apparent “Quantum Entanglement” phenomenon merely represents the UCP’s computation of “equivalent SST particle points” along the MST’s (subatomic) “wave” computation, which is embedded within the broader EST UCP’s computation! Alongside “G-D’s Physics” new (profound) theoretical understanding, wherein the UCP’s computation of the four basic physical features of “space” and “energy”, “mass” and “time” is based on the UCP’s two (out of three) “Computational Dimensions” i.e., “Framework” and “Consistency” four possible combinations: “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), and “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) possible combinations! Hence, “G-D’s Physics” new theoretical framework has been shown capable of resolving this apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between GRT’s strict SLB’s principle constraint imposed upon the transmission of any signal (or even information) across space and time – which seems to be contradicted by Quantum Entanglement’s “instantaneous” effect of the measurement of one entangled particle’s complimentary pairs’ measurement upon the other entangled particle’s complimentary value; based on the deeper theoretical understanding of “G-D’s Physics” (novel) conceptualization and understanding wherein it is the simultaneous UCP’s computation of “equivalent MST wave” “particle-points”, coupled with its two “Computational Dimensions” complimentary exhaustive UCP’s computation of “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”), which can account for the apparent “entanglement” of two such “equivalent SST particle points” along the “MST wave” (simultaneous) computation of the UCP’s “complimentary-exhaustive” “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) “complimentary pairs”!

Likewise, the New “G-D’s Physics” theoretical framework offer a new (satisfactory) alternative theoretical explanation for the universe’s empirically observed accelerated expansion! This new theoretical explanation of “G-D’s Physics” is based on its (novel) “Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis” (CHCFH) which stipulated that whenever there is a large group of individual human-beings all collectively focusing on this singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP), then this brings about an “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE), e.g., such as during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashanah” (New Year) two days’ special time interval (in which Millions of Jews all over the world collectively focus on this singular UCP) – which was predicted to bring about such an “UNCIARE” increase in the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion!

c) Identification of at least one unique “Critical Prediction” which can differentiate the prediction of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm from the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT & QM: according to Kuhn’s [50], analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”, in order for any scientific discipline to accept a basic “Paradigmatic-Shift” from the Old (“Material-Causal”) Paradigm to the New (“G-D’s Physics”) Paradigm it is necessary to identify at least one unique “Critical Prediction” that can differentiate the predictions of the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm from the Old “Material-Causal” GRT’s and QM’s predictions! Indeed, if at least one such (unique) “Critical Prediction” of the New “G-D’s Physics” Paradigm is verified as “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of the Old Paradigm’s GRT’s & QM’s predictions – then (according to Kuhn’s[50] well accepted analysis) that particular scientific discipline (e.g., in our case Theoretical Physics) has to accept the New “G-D’s Physics” as the New (satisfactory) Physics Paradigm (for the Twenty-First Century)! Indeed, we’ve been blessed with such an identification of two such (unique) “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm – which are being shown to be “more valid” than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM, therefore leading to the unequivocal acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” as the New Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century!

Methods & Results

In order to directly contrast between the New “G-d’s Physics” (CUFT) Paradigm and the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, “G-d’s Physics” identified a unique “Critical-Prediction” stemming from its new “computational definitions” of the four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time” – based on the UCP’s singular higher-ordered two “Computational Dimensions” of “Framework” (frame/object) and “Consistency” (consistent/inconsistent): According to this new UCP’s Computational Dimensions definition of the “mass” of any given particle as an “object-consistent” computational measure:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} [UF(n)] = O(i..n\{o-x,o-y,o-z\} \{UF(i..n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i..n)\}$$

where the UCP’s computational measure of the “mass” value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the “Object-consistent” “internal” {o-x,o-y,o-z} values across a given series of UF’s frames remains constant (e.g., identical):

such that:

$$M: [O_i\{x,y,z\}UF's(i)] - O_n\{x,y,z\}UF's(i..n) \leq n * h \{UF's(i..n)\}$$

Wherein the UCP’s computational measure of “mass” represents its computation of the number of UF’s frame/s in which the “Object-consistent” internal values cannot exceeds a minimal increase based on a multiplication of the number of UF’s frames by Planck’s constant value.

“G-d’s Physics” unique “Critical-Prediction” predicts that relatively “more-massive” particles such as the (negatively charged) “Muon” would be measured as more “spatially-consistent” than an equivalently (negatively charged) “electron” particle! This unique “G-d’s Physics” “Critical-Prediction” was de-facto tested by the “Proton-Radius Puzzle” associated experiments conducted by Pohl et al. (2010) :

The “Proton-Radius Puzzle” Confirms “G-D’s Physics” Critical Prediction

Pohl et al.[54-56], set to measure the radius of a Hydrogen Proton – contrasting between the Standard Hydrogen surrounded by the (negatively charged) electron, and a “Muonic Hydrogen” in which its electron was replaced by a much more massive (negatively charged) “Muon” particle; Surprisingly, they found that the Proton radius was greatly decreased in the Muonic-Hydrogen, than in the Standard Hydrogen – which they termed as the “Proton-Radius Puzzle”, because it could not be satisfactorily accounted for by Relativistic or Quantum Models?!

In contrast, these findings conform and validate the unique "Critical-Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm stemming from its above-mentioned new UCP's computational definition of the "mass" of any given subatomic particle:

$$M: \sum \{O_i\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} \{UF(n)\} = O(i \dots n\{o-x, o-y, o-z\} \{UF(i \dots n)\} / h * n\{UF's(i \dots n)\}$$

where the UCP's computational measure of the "mass" value of any given object is computed based on the number of times in which the "Object-consistent" "internal" $\{o-x, o-y, o-z\}$ values across a given series of UF's frames remains constant (e.g., identical).

This is because according to the New "G-d's Physics" UCP's computational definition of the "mass" value of any given subatomic particle, a more massive a particle possesses more "spatially-consistent" physical features – therefore predicting the "Critical-Prediction" of the relatively "more-massive" Muonic Hydrogen Proton possessing a more "spatially-consistent", i.e., smaller and more accurate, than the relatively "less-massive" electron-associated Standard Hydrogen Proton measurements!

Noteworthy is the fact that this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-d's Physics" Paradigm regarding the more "spatially-consistent" measurements of the relatively more massive "Muon-Hydrogen" as opposed to the relatively less-massive "electron-Hydrogen" – could not be accounted for by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of RT & QM (e.g., despite various attempts to explain this "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings: the "three-body force"[49], interactions between gravity and the weak force, or a flavour-dependent interaction [53,57], higher dimension gravity [48], a new boson [52], and the quasi-free hypothesis

$\pi+$ [51]; and therefore constitutes a direct empirical validation of this New "G-d's Physics" (CUFT) Paradigm!

The "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG) Confirms "G-D's Physics" "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Another means for testing a unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm relates to the "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE) due to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus (CHCF) associated with the two days' "Rosh-Hashana" time-interval in which Millions of Jews are collectively focusing upon this singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP; In contrast to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's GRT purely hypothetical "dark-matter" or "dark-energy" concepts ensuing "constant-rate" of the universe's expansion acceleration – which should not increase with time! Based on the New "G-D's Physics" "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" which assumes that the accelerated rate of the universe's expansion undergoes a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion", at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashana" two days' special time-interval! An indirect empirical validation of this unique "Critical Prediction" of the New "G-D's Physics" Paradigm was already given based on the unexplained findings regarding the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap" (UACAREG)!

Empirically, a basic (unexplained) "gap" exists between the universe's measured initial Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) measurement rate of expansion indices, e.g., of approximately 67 Kilometers per second per megaparsec – as opposed to 74 kilometers per second per megaparsec in later Astronomical measures of the universe's (contemporary) rate of expansion [58-61]?! This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) negates the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm's assumption of the existence of (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter" and "dark-energy" concepts as "causing" the accelerated rate of the uni-

verse's expansion; because even if such (purely hypothetical) "dark-matter"/"dark-energy" concepts existed (e.g., which failed to be detected after two decades of experimentation), according to the New "G-d's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm they could not interact (directly or indirectly) with any constituting element of the universe "causing" it to accelerate the rate of the universe's expansion! Therefore, they could not result in the observed CAAEG "Universe's Non-Continuous Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCARE)!

Therefore, the abovementioned results unequivocally validate and support two unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm – as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM: as indicated by the "Proton-Radius Puzzle" findings, and by the "Universe's Astronomical-Cosmological Accelerated Rate of Expansion Gap"! In this respect (as stated above), we now stand at an equivalent "historic juncture" to Eddington's 1919 Solar Eclipse empirical validation of Einstein's GRT's "Critical Prediction" regarding Mercury's double-valued Perihelion curvature around the Sun – which validated Einstein's GRT as more valid than the Older Newtonian Mechanics Paradigm! This is because the empirical validations of these two (abovementioned) "Critical Predictions" indicate that "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is more valid and exhaustive than the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm underlying GRT and QM, and in fact includes both of them as "special cases" within the broader, more exhaustive theoretical framework of "G-D's Physics" newly discovered Universal Computational Formula (UCF) (as outlined above).

Discussion

We've reached a fundamental pivotal "turning-point" or a very basic "Paradigmatic-Shift" in our whole scientific understanding and appreciation of the origin- true nature- and indeed whole "Goal" of the universe's (continuous and ongoing) creation of the entire physical universe! No longer can we perceive of the universe as an "independent" "objective" "physical" reality that exists "continuously", was "caused" by an initial "Big-bang" nuclear event, and that is being governed by (random) "material-causal" physical interactions between a finite set of physical entities!? For the first time (in Physics), the entire physical universe has been "transformed" into being perceived as a mere "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Reality" (UCR) (or "Universal Computational Principle", UCP) which solely exists both "during" its (simultaneous) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s, as well as solely existing "in-between" any two (such) consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., without the presence of any physical universe)!

The universe could not have been created (or "caused") by any initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event, nor can its (empirically observed) accelerated rate of expansion be "caused" by the purely hypothetical (and in fact "non-existent") "dark-matter" concept because there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "cause-and-effect" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) that exist either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

"G-D's Physics New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm

We realize that the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of (20th century) General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM) are challenged – (and indeed revised –) based on "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm! This is because according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- "Universal Frames" (UF's), due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's (UCR's) computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/s! In order to "demonstrate" this

New "A-Causal Computation" "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm a "Mercury-Ball & Glass Jar" Cinematic-Film Metaphor was utilized: Imagine a scenario in which a "Mercury-Ball" is depicted as "impacting" another "Glass-Jar" (filled with water), which seems to "cause" the "breakage" of this "Glass-Jar" and consequent "water-spillage"... However, if we opt to "slow-down" the progression of the film-frames (sequence), and even "halt" it (altogether), we would be surprised to find out that at none of these "separate" "film-frames", can there exist any such "cause-and-effect" physical relationship/s between this "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" (e.g., thereby negating the very possibility of the existence of such a "material-causal" relationship between the "impact" of the "Mercury-Ball" upon the "Glass-Jar", which could "cause" its breakage and consequent "water-spillage")! This is because (upon further inspection of each individual "film-frame" separately) we would find out that at none of these "film-frames" ("separately") can there exist any such "cause-and-effect" physical interaction/s between these two "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" objects – since they are being presented "simultaneously" in each of these "film-frames"! Indeed, we see that at each of these (consecutive) "film-frames" both the "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" are being presented "simultaneously" and hence there cannot exist any "cause-and-effect" relationship/s between them?! Moreover, "in-between" any two such consecutive "film-frames" there exists a "pure light beam", which "separates" between them so that there cannot also exist any such "cause-and-effect" (or "material-causal") physical relationships between the "Mercury-Ball" and "Glass-Jar" appearing in one "film-frame" and their appearance in any subsequent "film-frame"! Instead, we realize that what appears as such a "cause-and-effect" physical relationship/s between the (heavy) "Mercury-Ball" and (fragile) "Glass-Jar" merely represents the "arrangement" of those "film-frames" (by the "Producer" of this film) in such a sequence in which there seems to exist an "increasing proximity" between them, up until their "conjoined-appearance", followed by the "shattering" of the "Glass-Jar"! In other words, what gives us the "impression" according to which there exists a "cause-and-effect" physical relationship/s between the (heavy) "Mercury-Ball's impact" upon the (delicate) "Glass-Jar's", and its "consequent breakage" is merely the result of the Producer's serial arrangement of these "film-frames" in an "ever-growing proximity" etc...

Indeed, "G-D's Physics" New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm utilizes this "Cinematic-Film: Mercury-Ball-Glass-Jar" Metaphor" to try and explain the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) for each consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby negating the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing in the same- or different- UF's frame/s)! According to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, e.g., existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s: due to the "simultaneity" of this UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frames, and the complete "dissolution" of all exhaustive spatial pixels (in the universe) back into the singularity of the UCP "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s! Instead, "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm asserts that it is solely the "arrangement" of the series of UF's frame/s by this singular higher-ordered UCP, which may give us the impression of the existence of certain "material-causal" physical relationship/s (or "laws") but (in truth), there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s!

In this manner, it was shown that the New "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm negates some of the most fundamental "Material-Causal" assumptions characterizing the Old "Material-Causal"

Paradigm, e.g., underlying both GRT & QM:

a) "G-D's Physics' A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm negates GRT's "Big-Bang" Model!

"G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm negates GRT's "Big-Bang" Model wherein it is assumed that the whole origination of the entire physical universe was "caused" by an initial "Big-Bang" nuclear event that created all of the suns, galaxies, planets, mass and energy in the universe!? This is simply because (once again), based on the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising the entire physical universe, e.g., for each consecutive UF's frame/s, and the complete "dissolution" of the entire universe (back into the singularity of the UCP) "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frames; therefore, there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- of different UF's frames – i.e., including between the assumed (initial) nuclear "Big-Bang" event and any (assumed "created") "suns", "galaxies", "matter" or "energy"! Hence also there could not have existed any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s between this assumed "Big-Bang" nuclear event and its creation of an expanding universe, including an increasing number of suns, galaxies, planets, "mass" and "energy" in the universe, e.g., in any subsequent UF's frame/s!

b) "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm Negates the (Purely Hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" Concept!

"G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm also negates the existence of the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" concept which is assumed to "cause" the accelerated expansion of the universe?! According to the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm of GRT (& QM), this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could yet not be detected (or verified) experimentally for the past full two decades?! Hence, apart from this "impossible state" of 20th century Theoretical Physics (of the Old GRT's Material-Causal Paradigm's assumption) wherein up to 95% of all mass in the universe is assumed to comprise this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept, which could not yet be validated experimentally (for over twenty years!?) The New "G-D's Physics A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm directly negates the very possibility of the existence of this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept strictly based upon the simultaneity of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising each consecutive UF's frame/s (and the complete "dissolution" of the entire physical universe back into the UCP's singularity "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frames) – which negates the very possibility of the existence of any "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels found within the same- or different- UF's frame/s, i.e., including between this (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter" concept and certain "galactic elements" (which is assumed to "cause" these "galactic elements" to expand outwardly, thereby brining about the accelerated expansion of the universe)! Even at a more fundamental computational level, the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm was shown to negate the basic "Self-Referential Computational Structure" of the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm, including GRT's SRCS Computational Structure, e.g., which includes "Dark-Matter" as one of its elements – based on "G-D's Physics" newly discovered "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP)!

"G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle's" (CDP) principle negation of the Old "Material-Causal" fundamental "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS): "G-D's Physics" "Computational Duality Principle" (CDP) analysis of the intrinsic "computational-flaw" characterizing the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm as a "Self-Referential Computational System" (SRCS) which inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency" and ensuing "computational indeterminacy"! As asserted by the abovementioned "G-d's Physics" Computational Duality Principle (CDP),

This "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG) indicates a SRNCS computational result yielded by the Old "Material-Causal" "Self-Referential Computational Structure" (SRCS):

SRNCS: {DM/DE, *Uec-er*} $ti \rightarrow$ {"Not *Uec-er*"} $ti+n$

wherein it is assumed that it is the direct (or indirect) physical interaction between (purely hypothetical) "Dark-Matter"/"Dark-Energy" (DM/DE concepts) and the "exhaustive components of the Universe- expansion rate" (*Uec-ar*) that "causes" the universe to increase its acceleration rate with time?!

But, as the CDP teaches us, such a SRNCS computational state inevitably leads to both "logical-inconsistency", e.g., an apparent contradiction between the universe's stated expansion rate at ti : as *Uec-er*; as opposed to its expansion rate as: Not *Uec-er* at $ti+n$?!

This "logical-inconsistency" also invariably leads to an associated "computational-indeterminacy" – simply because such assumed SRCS(SRNCS) computational System is unable to decide whether the universe's accelerated rate should be "*Uec-er*" (at ti) or "Not *Uec-er*" (at $ti+n$) ?!

But, since according to the CDP we obtain clear empirical results (stated above) wherein the universe in fact exhibits an increase in its acceleration rate over time, e.g., as indicated by the "Cosmological-Astronomical Accelerated Expansion Gap" (CAAEG), therefore the CDP asserts that the basic SRCS/SRNCS Computational System assumed by the Old "Material-Causal" Paradigm (of RT & QM) must be negated and rejected!

Instead, "G-d's Physics" New Paradigm's CDP points at the existence of the singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of " $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ sec⁻¹"), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every consecutive "minimal time-point"!

c) "G-D's Physics A-Causal Computation" Paradigm Negates "Darwin's Natural Selection Principle"!

"G-D's Physics A-Causal Computation" Paradigm was also shown to negate Darwin's Natural Selection Principle (DNSP) Evolutionary Theory, also based on the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF's frame/s; this is simply because DNSP assumes the existence of (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between a certain Cosmic Radiation and its "causing" of specific "genetic-mutations" in a particular organism, which is (subsequently) associated with another assumed (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction between this "genetically-mutated organism" and a "Challenging Environment" – which "causes" this (particular) "genetically-mutated organism" to be "more compatible" to this "Challenging Environment", and hence "survive" (better) than the other "genetically non-mutated organism/s", thereby passing its "genetically-mutated information" to "next generation mutated organisms"; But, this basic NSDP is negated by "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm – once again, due to the UCP's "simultaneous" computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive UF's frame/s), which negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different-UF's frame/s! This includes the negation of the possibility of the existence of any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions between any "Cosmic Radiation" and "genetic mutation/s" in any given organism, or between any such (assumed) "genetically mutated organism" and (assumed) "Challenging Environment" (e.g., in any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s)! Therefore, according to the New "G-D's Physics"

"A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationship/s between those "Cosmic-Rays" and the "genetically mutated organism", nor between this (assumed) "genetically-mutated" organism and a "Challenging Environment" (which was assumed by DNSP to "cause" the "survival" of only these "genetically-mutated organism's" offspring)!? Instead, according to "G-D's Physics" New "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm, the only manner in which we can explain the whole origination- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe, e.g., including its Physical and Biological developments is totally dependent upon our deeper understanding (and appreciation) of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP or "Universal Consciousness Reality", UCR)!

So, we reach the inevitable conclusion wherein the entire physical universe does not exist as a "solid", "continuous" physical reality, but only exists as a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the this singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR), which solely exists: "continuously", "uniformly" and "constantly" (e.g., both "during" its consecutive computation of each subsequent UF's frame, and also solely exists "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's frame/s)! This ("startling") discovery (and realization) of "G-D's Physics" "Computational Invariance Principle" and "Universal Consciousness Reality" theoretical postulates, e.g., that the entire physical universe is only a "transient-phenomenal" manifestation of the only ("computationally-invariant") "Universal Consciousness Reality"; coupled with "G-D's Physics" "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm, which negates the very possibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical relationships between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels (existing either in the same- or different-) UF's frame/s (due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels' (four physical features) for every consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete "dissolution" of all such exhaustive spatial pixels (for each UF's frame/s) "in-between" any two consecutive UF's frame/s (back into the singularity of the UCP); points at the fact that the whole physical universe is being continuously produced (or computed) solely by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR – rather than being "dependent" upon any (direct or indirect) "material-causal" physical interaction/s (e.g., at the relativistic or quantum levels)!? In fact, as we've seen, no such (direct or even indirect) "material-causal" physical interactions can exist either "during" any consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., due to the "simultaneity" of the UCP's computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels comprising any given single UF's), nor "in-between" any two such consecutive UF's (in which all of these exhaustive spatial pixels "dissolve" back into the singularity of the UCP/UCR)!?

We are therefore led to the new profound theoretical understanding, wherein there only exists one singular higher-ordered "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR) which exists both "during" its consecutive computation of every consecutive UF's frame/s, as well as exists "in-between" any two such consecutive frames (without the presence of any physical universe)! The physical universe does not exist as a "continuous", "independent" or "constant" phenomenon – but is rather being continuously "created", "dissolved", "re-created" and "evolved" by this singular higher-ordered UCR! This profound new realization of "G-D's Physics" (empirically proven) New Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm inevitably also led to the investigation of this singular higher-ordered UCR's Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD's) that are directly responsible for the continuous "creation"- ("dissolution")- "sustenance"- and "evolution"- of every exhaustive spatial pixel/s in the universe (as well as the development of the whole universe)!

The Universal Consciousness Reality's (UCR) "Ten-Hierarchical Computational Dimensions":

These THCD's represent some of the UCP's intrinsic characteristics portraying the primary "motivation", "propensities" and "Ultimate Geulah

Goal" of the UCP's continuous origination- sustenance- and development of the entire physical universe (towards this "Ultimate Geulah Perfected State" of the universe and Humanity)!

1) The UCR's "Wisdom/Free-Will" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חכמה"):

The UCP's first Hierarchical Computational Dimension is termed: the UCP's "Wisdom/Free-Will" ("All-Goodness") wish to create an apparently "separate" and "independent" physical universe (of the "true singularity" of the "Universal Consciousness Reality" (UCR)! – towards the fulfillment of its "Ultimate Geulah Goal" of a "Perfected" (Morally, Spiritually and even Physically) State of Humanity (and the universe)! It represents the UCP's/UCR's initial "Wisdom/Free-Will" and "Goodwill" impetus towards creating an apparently "independent" physical universe (e.g., from its true sole "Universal Consciousness Reality's" sustenance of it) that will "evolve" from inanimate "matter" through "animate" (plants, animals and human-beings) leading to the "Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State" of Humanity (and Science) that will recognize (and appreciate) the singularity of this UCR's, its "Infinite Wisdom", "All-Goodness", "Moral" etc. Characteristics!

2) The UCP's Conscious-Moral Development (CMD) Blueprint Plan ("בינה"):

The UCP's secondary Hierarchical Computational Dimension is its "Conscious-Moral Development Blueprint Plan" ("בינה") relates to the UCP's overall "Blueprint Plan" on how to evolve the entire physical universe from its initial "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings, and up to Humanity's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State"! Surprisingly, we find that the whole development of all "inanimate" forms and then all "animate" Biological forms (e.g., of plants, animals and human-beings) has already been "pre-planned" by the UCP – e.g., before the "actual" creation of the entire physical universe (and throughout the continuous computation- dissolution- re-creation- and evolution- of every consecutive UF's frame/s, this "UCP's CMD Blueprint Plan" serves as the basis for the ongoing creation sustenance and development of the entire universe)!

3) The UCR's Consistency Computation ("Daat"/ דעת"):

The UCR's third Hierarchical Computational Dimension relates to its "Consistency" Computation relating to the manner in which this singular (higher-ordered) UCP executes- and manifests- its (two previous) Blueprint Plan for "steering" the entire physical universe towards the "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State! Essentially, in order to "advance" and "evolve" the entire physical universe towards its "Perfected Geulah State", the UCP "employs" several of its "Consistency Computation Mechanisms", i.e., pertaining to "Physical Consistency", "Conscious-Moral Development Consistency", "Moral Consistency" and "Geulah Driven Development Consistency"! Succinctly explained (see all previous detailed: Bentovish articles), the UCP computes "Physical Consistency" based on the (four possible) combinations of two Computational Dimensions of "Consistency" (e.g., "consistent" or "inconsistent") and "Framework" ("frame" or "object") – yielding the four basic physical features of "Space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (as outlined above and previously)! The UCP employs a "Conscious-Moral Development Consistency" computation relating to the development of the various "progressively more expansive manifestation" forms of this "Universal Consciousness Reality": from "inanimate matter" through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings! The UCP also employs a "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle Consistency" computation, which essentially computes for every individual human-being (for each consecutive UF's frame/s) one of "multiple possible future/s" that precisely "corrects", "balances" or "reinforces" this individual human-being's specific "moral/immoral choice", such that he/she will have to experience the same "moral/immoral" situation created by this individual human-being! Finally, the UCP also employs a "Geulah Driven Develop-

ment Consistency" computation pertaining to the UCP's "steering" of the universe towards this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! It is important to note (as explained previously) that these "Three Key Initial Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (TKI-HCD's) serve as the "basis" for the UCP's ongoing continuous computation- "dissolution"- sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe for each consecutive UF's frame/!

4) The fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("חסד"/Chessed"):

This fourth "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" relates to the UCP's actual execution of the (abovementioned) "UCP's Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle Consistency" computation – as it pertains to each individual human-being, based on his/her "moral/immoral choice/s" (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), which is geared towards "reinforcing" or "correcting" any "moral"/"immoral choice/s" that any individual human-being is making at any "point in time" – based on the selection of "one of multiple possible future/s" (from the "UCP's Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" of all "past", "present" or "multiple possible futures")! It advances each individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) towards attaining the UCP's Ultimate "Geulah Goal Perfected State" by teaching us that we are truly "inseparable" from other and from this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality" – which is characterized by "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony"!

5) The Fifth UCR's "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("Gevurah"/גבורה):

The fifth "Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" HCD relates to the UCP's computation of the "assembly" of all individual-based UCP's "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle's" "reinforcements" or "corrections" to form the overall "bank" of the "Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" of all "past"- "present"- or "multiple possible future/s" UF's pertaining to all individual human-beings (based on their "moral/immoral interactions")! It is (obviously) almost "inconceivable" (for our limited human mind, or even for any "Supercomputer") to "envision" how could this "Universal Consciousness Reality" compute such a "Supra Spatial-Temporal Reservoir" – for "reinforcing" or "correcting" all the (over 8 Billion) individual human-beings (e.g., relative to all of their possible present- and past- interactions with all other human-beings they came in some contact with); but this only demonstrates the "Infinite Wisdom" of this singular "Universal Consciousness Reality", which "remembers"- "sustains"- "dissolves"- "re-computes"- and "evolves"- every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, and every individual human-being's "moral/immoral choice/s" for each consecutive UF's frame/s, so many "trillions" of times each second! But, once again, we have to bear in mind that the sole "purpose" or "Goal" of this singular UCR Reality is to steer the entire universe and Humanity towards the realization of the Ultimate "Geulah- Goal Perfected State" of the universe!

6) The UCR's "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("תפארת"/Tiferet):

the sixth Hierarchical Computational Dimension is the "UCP's Collective Human Consciousness Focus Hypothesis" which postulates that the actual manifestation of the entire physical universe – is "divided up" into "yearly intervals" that critically depend upon the "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (UCP's) close relationship with a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" (e.g., a large group of human-beings all "focusing" upon this UCP at a particular "special time-interval")! In other words, according to "G-d's Physics" New 21st century Paradigm, the UCR's actual computation of all past- present and "multiple possible future/s" Universal Frames (UF's) constituting each consecutive Year's (time-interval) critically depends upon such "Collective Human Consciousness Focus", in which Millions of individual human-beings simultaneously focus on this singular higher-ordered UCR during a "special time-interval", i.e., such as at the Jewish "Rosh-Hashanah" New Year two-days' time-interval in which

Millions of Jews focus collectively upon this singular higher-ordered UCR! Indeed, one of the (two abovementioned) unique "Critical Predictions" of the New "G-D's Physics" Scientific Paradigm, differentiating it from the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM precisely relates to this "special-time interval" of such a "Collective Human Consciousness Focus" that takes place every Jewish New-Year's "Rosh-Hashanah" two days' time interval (e.g., which occurred during the last Jewish year at: Sep. 6th & 7th, 2022), in which it is predicted that there will be a "Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion" of the entire physical universe! As noted above, this "Universe's Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (UNCIARE) received a direct empirical validation based on the empirically observed "Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe's Accelerated Rate of Expansion" (CAGUARE)!

7) The UCP's "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal"):

Signifies the UCR's actual simultaneous computation of all Individual human-beings' (two- out of four) basic "Object - "consistent" ("mass") and "inconsistent" ("time") values for each (single) UF frame - that is "derived" from the UCP's previous HCD's (cumulative) computations! It represents the beginning of the actual manifestation of any single UF's frame's computation of all Individual human-beings, that fulfills (and advances) the UCR's "Reversed-Time Geulah Goal Perfected State" (and manifests the "UCP's Collective Human Consciousness Focus" computation of an entire New Year's UF's frames - i.e., being executed for each single UF's frame's individual human-beings' (two) "mass" and "time" values! It is also represented by the Jewish Chassidic-Kabbalah symbol of "נצח" "Eternal" or "Victory" because the UCR's actual computation of any single UF frame's comprising Object's (mass and time) values all constituting objects indeed signifies the advancement of the UCR's ("Reversed Time") Geulah Goal Hierarchical Computational Dimension", which represents the "Eternal" or Ultimate "Geulah -State" of the universe!

8) The "Teshuva" ("תשובה")/"הוד"/"Hod"/"Forgiveness" Hierarchical Computational Dimension:

Signifies the UCR's allowance for a "Teshuva"/ "repentance" of every individual human-being prior to the actual execution of the seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal" - wherein if any individual person chooses to ask "forgiveness" from the other person upon which it inflicted pain or suffering, as well as from the Universal Consciousness Reality (UCR) and makes a conscious resolute decision - to "avoid" repeating any such "immoral action/s (which constitutes the Jewish term of "Teshuva"); in such case, the UCR's (eighth) "Teshuva" Hierarchical Computational Dimension will re-compute, i.e., and (in fact) "alter" the already selected Seventh "Computed Object Potential Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("נצח"/"Netzach"/"Eternal") computed for that individual human-being (who made such a "Teshuva"); replacing the (otherwise) "correcting" equivalent UF frame" in which this "offending" individual human-being would have to experience an "equivalent negative experience" (to the one experienced by the person offended by his/her "immoral choice"), with a "positive" immediate future UF frame - based on the fact that that individual human-being already made "Teshuva" (sincere repentance and resolute decision not to repeat any such "immoral" action/s!)

9) The UCR's "Actual Computed Object Values Hierarchical Computational Dimension" ("יסוד"/"Yesod" (Foundation)):

Signifies the UCR's actual computation of those (two) basic ("Object"- "consistent" or "inconsistent") physical features, e.g., of "mass" and "time" for all individual human-beings (for each consecutive UF's frame/s), based on all previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions!) Note, however, that this "יסוד"/"Foundation" Ninth Hierarchical

Computational Dimension does not (yet) contain the two other UCP's basic ("Frame" - "consistent" and "inconsistent") physical features of "energy" and "space", e.g., that are necessary to execute the actual (prospective single) UF frame of the universe at any minimal time-point (e.g., that is computed by the Tenth Hierarchical Computational Dimension)!

10) The "Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula"/"מלכות"/"Malchut" (Kingdom) Hierarchical Computational Dimension ("כתר"/"Keter-Infinity" ("Crown")):

This (tenth "concluding") Hierarchical Computational Dimension signifies the UCR's actual computation of each consecutive Universal Frame (UF), including all of its four basic physical features of "Object" - "consistent" (mass) and "inconsistent" (time), and "Frame" - "consistent" (space) and "inconsistent" (energy) - for each Individual human-being (at every consecutive UF's frame/s)! It "consumes" all of the previous Hierarchical Computational Dimensions as comprising any single consecutive UF's frame/s, thereby executing and "leading" each Individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) towards the fulfillment of the UCP's "Ultimate Geulah -Goal Perfected State" of the universe!

We therefore see, that the "true nature" of the universe is that it is (truly) solely comprised of this singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle/Reality" (UCP/UCR)! Moreover, we realize the great "elegance" ("beauty") of this singular UCR in "steering" the entire physical universe towards its "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State", e.g., by computing at each "trillionth of trillionth etc. of a second" ($c^2/h = 1.36 \times 10^{50}$ sec!) those THCD's - that are "advancing" Humanity and the universe towards the (inevitable) fulfillment of this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State"! In fact, "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm is also "closing an (important) circle", in that it offers a new ("hopeful" and "moral") alternative to the Old "Material-Causal" (e.g., "accidental" or "random") creation- and development- (towards an apparent "disintegration") of the universe - since (as noted above), the development (and continuous "dissolution", "re-creation" and "development" of the entire physical universe has been "pre-planned" based on the UCP's TIK-HCD's to reach its "Ultimate Perfected (Moral, Spiritual and even Physical) Geulah State"! In fact, with the (current) direct empirical validations of "G-D's Physics" (two abovementioned unique) "Critical Predictions" - not only must Science "embrace" this New "G-D's Physics" as the new (satisfactory) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century - but (in fact) points at the beginning of this UCP's Ultimate Perfected Geulah State of Humanity and the Universe (since 21st century Theoretical Physics is recognizing and accepting "G-D's Physics" sole UCR reality as being characterized through its THCD's including It being characterized by certain ("intrinsic-sublime") characteristics such as "Morality", "All-Goodness", "Peace" and "Harmony" as "Steering" the universe towards this "Perfected Geulah State"! "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm alters and "resolves" those apparent "theoretical inconsistencies" - both between GRT & QM (as shown above), as well as completely transforms (and "resolves") "Gödel's (Logic-Mathematics) Incompleteness Theorem" (GIT), as outlined previously) by pointing out through its "Computational Duality Principle", that whereas any "GIT-like" "Self-Referential Negative Computational System" (SRNCS) inevitably leads to both "logical inconsistency" and "computational indeterminacy" - due to the singular UCP's empirically proven capacity to compute all Physical, Biological, and "Deductive-Logic-Mathematical" Systems' outcomes, therefore it inevitably points at the singular and sole UCR reality which creates- sustains- "dissolves"- recreates- and develops- the whole universe towards Humanity's "Ultimate Perfected Geulah State" (which is currently beginning with the empirical validation of "G-D's Physics" New Scientific Paradigm's two unique "Critical Predictions")!

The UCP'S "Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions – Universal Computational Formula" (THCD's-UCF):

"G-D's Physics Complete Unification of GRT & QM, The Four Physical Features & Four Forces of Nature!"

Another (highly significant) theoretical achievement of this New "G-D's Physics" (empirically validated) "A-Causal Computation" Scientific Paradigm is its shown capacity to offer a satisfactory solution for the key unresolved "enigma" of Twenty-First Century's Theoretical Physics is the "Gravitational Enigma" (GE), i.e.: Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of "gravitation" which can: a) Unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); and b) Offer an alternative satisfactory explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion that is not based on the purely hypothetical "Dark-Matter" (DM) concept (which is assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe but could not be detected even after two full decades of intensive experimentation?!); c) Unify between the Gravitational Force and the other Three Forces (e.g., Strong- & Weak- Nuclear Forces and the Electromagnetic Force!); d) Offer an alternative theoretical explanation for the "curvature of Space-Time" by "massive objects" (e.g., based on the G-D'S PHYSICS' New Scientific "A-Causal Computation" Paradigm); Thus far, the "Gravitational Force" has been explained based on GRT's key assumption wherein this "Gravitational Force" (GF) is responsible for the "curvature of Space-Time" – i.e., without actually explaining its underlying "nature". Moreover, this assumed GF remains "inexplicable" (and "independent") of the Standard Model's proven capacity to unify between those other Three Forces, based on the discovery of elementary subatomic particles' interactions, and therefore is seen an unresolved "Gravitational Enigma"?! The purpose of this article is to try and offer an alternative solution for this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) based on the discovery of a New "G-d's Physics" Scientific Paradigm [1-30].

The potential capacity of this New G-D'S PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm to resolve this "Gravitational Enigma" (GE) stems from its discovery of a singular higher-ordered "Universal Computational Principle" (UCP) which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g., at the incredible rate of "c²/h" = 1.36⁻⁵⁰ sec⁻¹!), thereby producing an extremely rapid series of "Universal Frames" (UF's) comprising the entire physical universe at every "minimal time-point"! Additionally, the UCP's simultaneous computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) across a series of (such) UF's frame/s yields the UCP's novel "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time" (for each exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe) – as being computed by this singular UCP, based on its two "Computational Dimensions" of "Framework" and "Consistency! According to this (new) G-D'S PHYSICS explanation, the UCP (simultaneously) computes these four basic physical features – including the "mass" value of each exhaustive spatial pixel (in the universe) based on the four possible combinations of those "Framework" (e.g., "frame" or "object") and "Consistency" ("consistent" or "inconsistent") "Computational Dimensions": Such that the UCP computes "Framework" – "consistent" vs. "inconsistent" computations, as the "space" and "energy" values of any given spatial pixel (across a given series of UF's); and "Object" – "consistent" or "inconsistent" computations, as the "mass" and "time" values (across a given UF's

series) (Figure 1):

Framework/Consist.	Frame	Object
Consistent	"Space"	"Mass"
Inconsistent	"Energy"	"Time"

FIGURE 1. UCP'S COMPUTATION OF FOUR PHYSICAL FEATURES

Intriguingly, these novel "G-D'S PHYSICS" UCP's "computational definitions" of the four basic physical features also led to the discovery of an "Universal Computational Formula" (Figure 2), which was shown to completely integrate these four basic physical features as secondary computational "by-products" of this singular (higher-ordered) UCP (for the first time in Physics)!

FIGURE 2. The "UNIVERSAL COMPUTATIONAL FORMULA" (UCF)

Note: which is accompanied by "G-D'S PHYSICS" computational (above) definitions of these four basic physical features of "space" and "energy", "mass" and "time"

The UCF's Relativistic Format:

in which GRT's (famous) "Energy-Mass Equivalence" is embedded within the UCF.

The UCF's Quantum Format:

in which "Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle's" ("complimentary pairs") are embedded as "special cases" within the UCF (see previously elaborated analysis of "G-D'S PHYSICS" or G-D'S PHYSICS).

Significantly, the first (abovementioned) facet of this New G-D's PHYSICS Scientific Paradigm's potential resolution of the GE's first component – i.e., a) Deciphering the underlying mechanism responsible for the phenomenon of “gravitation” which can both unify between General Relativity Theory (GRT) and Quantum Mechanics (QM); is given through this (singular higher-ordered) UCP's (in-depth) analysis of the (true) “computational basis” of the “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM stems: According to the New G-D'S PHYSICS's computational analysis, this “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from GRT's strict “Speed of Light Barrier” for the transmission of any “signal” (or even “information”) across “space” and “time” – which seems to be “contradicted” by QM's “Quantum Entanglement Phenomenon”, indicating that the measurement of one “entangled particle” “instantaneously” affects the “complimentary” (“space/energy” or “mass/time”) measurement of the other “entangled particle”?! But, according to the new CUT's Paradigm, the (alternative) explanation- and “resolution”- of this apparent “GRT-QM theoretical inconsistency” stems from the UCP's singular (higher-ordered simultaneous) computation of all “Single Spatial-Temporal” computation (“SST”): “particle” of relativistic “object” (e.g., relating to only “one” spatial-temporal point, at any given moment), “Multi Spatial-Temporal” computation (MST): “wave” (e.g., relating to at least “two” points being measured at any point in time) or “Exhaustive Spatial Temporal” (EST) computation (e.g., relating to all “exhaustive” spatial pixels comprising an entire “Universal Frame”, UF), across a series of UF's frames (Figure 3);

UCP's Computations	SST	MST	EST
Num. “ST” Points	1	2+	All Points

FIGURE 3. UCP'S “SST”, “MST” & “EST” COMPUTATIONS

A “Gimatria-Based Consistency Computation” of Objects!

Based on the discovery of the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm, and its shown capacity to resolve the apparent “theoretical inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and more importantly, its empirical validation of two of its unique “Critical Predictions”, as more valid than the corresponding predictions of both GRT & QM; we now reach another “pivotal point” along the development of this New “G-D's Physics” Paradigm of 21st century Theoretical Physics: Since the New “G-D's Physics” Paradigm stipulated an “A-Causal Computation” stemming from the discovery of a singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational Principle” (UCP) which simultaneously computes every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe, which points at the impossibility of the existence of any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels, existing either in the same- or different UF's frame/s, then this points at the need for this singular higher-ordered UCP to compute all exhaustive spatial pixels (comprising the entire physical universe) for each consecutive UF's frame/s! However, thus far, the New “G-D's Physics” Paradigm's discovered “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions' Universal Computational Formula” (THCD-UCF) was only capable of explaining (in general terms) the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features (e.g., of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”) based on its stipulated two (out of three) “Computational Dimensions” (of “Consistency” and “Framework”) combinations! In other words, those four basic physical features are computed by this singular UCP as “Frame” – “consistent” (“space”) or “inconsistent” (“energy”), or as “Object” – “consistent” (“mass”) or “inconsistent” (“time”) computational measures of the degree of “consistency” or “inconsistency” of any given exhaustive spatial pixel's “object” across a series of UF's frames!

Moreover, the general (overall) conception of the origination- sustenance- and “Ultimate Goal” of the universe's development by this singular

UCP has given us an overall (good) overall understanding of the general framework for “G-D's Physics” New scientific explanation of the universe's existence and development; What's still “missing” is a “minute-detailed” understanding of the manner in which this UCP “differentiates” between its computation of these four basic physical features for every individual “object”;i.e., “inanimate” or “animate”! The suggested new “Gimatria Consistency Computation” (GCC) “fills” this “gap” and offers a new conceptual explanation for the manner in which this UCP can compute those four basic physical features (e.g., as “differentiating” their values for any specific “inanimate” or “animate” object)! The basic assumption underlying this new “GCC” facet of “G-D's Physics” THCD-UCF is that based on the (Hebrew) Alphabet's “naming” of every such (“animate” or “inanimate”) object, the UCP computes those four (integrated) basic physical features, e.g., through the usage of the five (subsequent) HCD (following the initial three “General Plan” of the UCP's origination and development of the physical universe, i.e., of “Wisdom”/”חכמה”, “Computation”/”בינה” & “Reversed Time Geulah Goal Consistency”/”דעת”)!

These five subsequent HCD comprise of: “Chessed”, “Gevorah”, “Tiferet”, “Neztach” & “Hod”, which are each stipulated to be comprised of the “ten total HCD's ten “zero's” minute temporal computation of the UCP – totaling the UCP's overall rate of computation for each exhaustive spatial pixel (for each consecutive UF's frame/s)! In other words, the manner in which the UCP can compute each and every exhaustive spatial pixel object's four basic physical features is based on a combination of its unique “name” – according to its “Gimateria” computation, based on those “subsequent five” (“Chessed”, “Gevorah”, “Tiferet”, “Neztach” & “Hod”) HCD detailing of each of the given “name's” (Hebrew) letters equivalent numeric value!

In other words, we obtain (e.g., for the first time in Theoretical Physics) a “Non-Material Gimateria Consistency Computation” (NMGCC) of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe! This new “G-D's Physics” NMGCC conception of the manner in which the singular higher-ordered UCP is capable of computing each and every “object” in the physical universe – based on its “Gimateria” (Hebrew Letters' numerical value) as representing the number of times that every exhaustive spatial pixel is presented across a certain series of UF's frames! Since we've already seen, that the UCP computes the “mass” value of any given object as its computation of the number of times this object has been presented (as “spatially-consistent”) across a series of UF's frames! This means that the current discovery of “G-D's Physics” New Paradigm's “NMGCC” capability of the UCP to “translate” the given “Gimatria” numerical value of any given “object's” (Hebrew) name into the UCP's computation of the five “secondary-essential” Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD): “Chessed”, “Gevorah”, “Tiferet”, “Neztach” & “Hod”, such that each of these HCD possesses all ten HCD's corresponding to “ten zero's” out of the “fifty zero's” representing the rate of the UCP's overall rate of UF's computation, i.e., $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)! This means for instance, that the Hebrew letters for the word “human-being” “אדם” comprise these three letters “א”, “ד”, “ם” which correspond to the “Gimatria” of “1-[1-10]”, “4-[11-20]” & “40-[21-30]” denoting the cumulative number of times that a “human-being” is presented across a series of UF's frames – with a special significance for the corresponding unique Gimateria numerical value for each of those (potential) five “secondary-essential” HCD “Chessed”, “Gevorah”, “Tiferet”, “Neztach” & “Hod”!) In other words, the specific (Hebrew) “Gimatria” for a “human-being” comprises a very unique and specific composition of three (out of the five) “secondary-essential” HCD: “Chessed”, “Gevorah” & “Tiferet”, with each one of them possessing a specific numerical value which can be translated to the UCP's computation of a human-being's “mass”, or in fact any other of the four (completely integrated) basic physical features (of “time”, “space” or “energy”), based on the earlier mentioned “Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions” – Universal Computational Formula” (THCD-UCF):

Noteworthy is the fact that we can perhaps “infer” some of these four basic

physical features based on the specific HCD's comprising each "object" – such as for instance, in the case of the UCP's computation of the four basic physical features of a "human-being" based on his Hebrew names specific "Gimateria" (three initial) HCD's numerical values, and understanding of the "corresponding" HCD's key characteristics: for instance, the fact that "אדם" only possesses the three initial HCD's of "Chessed", "Gevurah" & "Tiferet" (but not the two subsequent "Netzach" & "Hod" HCD), indicating that the UCP's computation of a "human-being" corresponding to the UCP characteristics of "Chessed": its natural tendency to "give" or to "nurture" (and "grow"), "Gevurah": the UCP's tendency to "measure" and "limit" its "giving" and "nurturance"; & "Tiferet": The UCP's capacity to "balance" and "integrate" between these apparently "opposing" ("Chessed" & "Gevurah") UCD (with a leaning towards the "Chessed" HCD in this "Tiferet" HCD)! More specifically, these three "Gimatria" Hebrew Letters' specific numerical value also indicates the relative significance of each of these three (initial HCD: "Chessed", "Gevurah" & "Tiferet"): Thus, for instance, the fact that amongst these three initial three HCD, it is primarily the "Tiferet" HCD which possesses the highest numerical value: "40-30" (sec!) implies the UCP's computation of a "human-being" is based upon the unique capacity of human-beings to "integrate" between the first letter of "א" associated with "Chessed": characterized by the Hebrew first letter "א" – which also represents "G-D" (since the Hebrew word for "G-D" is "אלוקים" which begins with this same "א" (Alef) letter and which is characterized by: "Goodness", "Giving", "Spirituality" etc.; and the second letter of "ד" (which also stands for the Hebrew word for "blood" signifying the "human body" – such that this integration of the "physical bodily" element with the "Divine" ("Spiritual") element is achieved and is also "leaning towards expressing" (more) the Divine element!

Interestingly, the Hebrew word for "Earth" or "soil" is very similar to Hebrew word for a "human-being" "אדמה" which has the addition of a fourth letter "ה" associated with the fourth "Secondary-essential" (five) "HCD's": "Netzach" נצח which signifies the UCP's capacity to "overcome any obstacle/s" for the fulfillment of its ultimate "Geulah Goal" of obtaining a "Perfected": "Moral" & "Spiritual" state of Humanity and the universe! This may imply that whereas a "human-being" is embedded with the characteristics of his ability to "integrate" and "uplift" his "bodily-material" nature with his "Divine" aspect, i.e., based on his given "Gevurah" and "Tiferet" HCD's; in the case of the Hebrew word for "Earth", the UCP adds the fourth HCD of "Netzach" which allows the "Earth" to serve as a "vehicle" to "manifest" and "overcome" any "obstacles" for the fulfillment of the UCP's ultimate "Geulah Goal Perfected State" of Humanity and of the universe!

Another pertinent example of the significance of this (newly discovered) "G-D's Physics" "Non-Material Gimateria Consistency Computation" (NMGCC) may be the Hebrew word for "G-D": "אלוקים" which comprises all of those "five" "secondary-essential" HCD's letters! Once again the first letter of the "Chessed" Dimension is "א" (Alef) which signifies not only the first letter of the Alphabet, but also represents "G-D"! The second letter is "ב" which represents the "Gevurah" HCD ("G-D's" "fierce force" of "overcoming any obstacles"); "ה" 5 in "Gimatria" for the third letter corresponding to the third "Tiferet" HCD signifying the UCP's capacity to "integrate" the five HCD's (as well as signifying the "third initial HCD's of "Binah" or "Computation, i.e., the UCP's capacity to organize, plan and compute the entire "Blue-Print Plan" of the whole development of the universe from its "inanimate" (initial) manifestation through "animate": plants, animals and human-beings towards the "Ultimate Geulah Goal" Perfected state of the universe)! The fourth letter is "ד" ("Yud" ("י")) standing for the "Netzach" HCD which is the UCP's ability to "overcome" and "triumph" over any "obstacles" in order to advance the whole universe towards its Ultimate "Geulah Goal Perfected" State! This is significant, because the "Yud" letter also characterizes "G-D" (e.g., appearing as the first letter in G-D's holy name), and possesses the "Gimatria" (10) representing the "Ten

Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" (which points at the fact that the UCP's capacity of "overcoming" and "obstacle/s" for the fulfillment of its Ultimate "Geulah-Goal Perfected State" of the universe stems from its THCD's overall "Blueprint Plan" and its execution towards attaining this "Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal"! The final (sixth) letter is "ו" for the fifth HCD of "Hod" which signifies (according to "G-D's Physics THCD) the UCP's enabling us as human-beings to do "Teshuva" (e.g., ask for "forgiveness" and "understanding" from "G-D", preceded by our conscious decision to "change our behavior" (for the better), and try our best not to "repeat" any "moral misdeeds"; This fifth "Hod" HCD also encompasses the aspect of us as human-beings recognizing the "Beauty", "Perfection" and "All-Goodness" of "G-D"!

So, we can see that the UCP's computation of every (possible) "object" (i.e., "inanimate" or "animate") is based upon its "Gimatria" of the Hebrew letters: e.g., which possess both significance in terms of the five "secondary-essential" Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (HCD's) to which they belong (according to their order: the first letter belonging to the "Chessed", second to "Gevurah" etc.) and their relative "Gimatria strength", e.g., both in terms of each Hebrew letter's "numerical value" and their associated HCD's value (i.e., "Chessed": from -1-10; "Gevurah": from -11 – 20; "Tiferet": from -21–30; "Netzach": -31 – 40 ; "Hod": from -41 – 50 !) Hence, an emerging new facet of this new NMGCC discovery made by "G-D's Physics" is the transformation of these Hebrew letters' "Gimatria": e.g., "numerical value" of each letter, combined with its association with each of those respective five "secondary-essential" HCD's – as determining the number of times that this object will be presented across a series of UF's frames: which would determine its "mass" value(!) But, as we've seen, another (not less important) facet of this (newly discovered) NMGCC is the relative significance of each of the letters/specific HCD (based on its Gimatria & HCD's "zero's strength", as "glanced" from the above examples) pertaining to each object's (Hebrew) letters.

One more significant discovery associated with this (novel) NMGCC perspective on how the UCP (continuously and simultaneously) computes all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe relates to those five "secondary-essential" HCD's differentiation between "human-beings", which possess a "free Moral Choice" and all other "inanimate and animate" forms which do not possess this "free Moral Choice"! This is due to the fact that the execution of those five "secondary-essential" HCD's depends on the UCP's "allowance" (and in fact "pre-planning") for human-beings to make those (precise) "free Moral Choice/s" as a part of its (overall) "Ultimate Geulah Goal", e.g., of "steering" Humanity (and the whole physical universe) towards that "Perfected Geulah State", in which all human-beings (and Humanity, as a whole) will recognize the "Oneness" of this singular "Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle" (or "Universal Consciousness Reality"), its innate characters of "Goodness", "Morality", "Peace" and "Harmony", and our "inseparability" from It (and from each other)! Indeed, when we (closely) examine those five "secondary-essential" HCD's we can sense that they are all "centered" or "anchored" in the UCP's "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP), e.g., whose "sole-aim" is to "teach" us (human-beings) our "inseparability" from this singular (higher-ordered) UCP – through our "free Moral Choice"! Thus, the "first" amongst those five "secondary-essential" HCD's is "Chessed's" "Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle" (DEMP)! This DEMP states that whenever any Individual human-being chooses an "Immoral Choice", e.g., towards another Individual human-being, which causes "pain" or "suffering" ("G-d forbid"), then this necessarily "triggers" the UCP's selection of an "equivalent negative situation", in which that Individual human-being that inflicted "pain/suffering" would have to "experience" the same "negative situation" – in order for us to realize that such "Immoral Choice/s" is not "right" and should be "avoided"! "Implicitly", since we begin "realizing" the "connection" that exists between any (negative) "Immoral Choice" that we may have made – and our own experiencing of such a "negative

situation” (e.g., of “pain or suffering”, “G-d forbid”), then this raises our “understanding” and “awareness” that we cannot make any such “Immoral Choices” but rather must “correct” our own “free Moral Choice/s” to constitute “positive Moral Choice/s”! (Once again, this implicit “Moral understanding” or “Moral awareness” that our “Moral/Immoral Choices” determine the “Moral/Immoral” “positive” or “negative” situations that we would experience (ourselves) makes us realize that we are really “inseparable” from each other, as “integral parts of this singular higher-ordered UCP!) Following this “Chesse’s” (HCD) “Dynamic-Equilibrium is the next HCD: “Gevurah” which possesses a “Multi Spatial-Temporal Reservoir” of all “past”, “present” and “multiple possible future/s” – for each Individual human-being depending upon (his or her) Moral/Immoral Choices (at each point in time), which already manifests the UCP’s computation of the specific future for each individual human –being based on their specific Moral Choice/s; Next, follows the “Tiferet” HCD’s Collective Human Consciousness Focus Jewish “Rosh Hashanah” (CHCF-JRH) “Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe” (NCAEU), in which the UCP essentially computes the specific “future/s” UF’s for all Individual human-beings for the entire next year (and which also correlates to the Collective Human Consciousness Focus’ “triggering” a “Non-Continuous Accelerated Expansion of the Universe”); Then, follows the HCD’s of “Neztach’s” “UCP’s Computed Potential Object”, corresponding to actually computed (next) “future UF’s” value/s for each Individual human-being (based upon the previous HD’s computation of the DEMP’s precise selected future for each Individual human-being etc.); and finally, the “fifth” HCD of “Hod’s” “UCP’s Teshuva”, in which the UCP allows for a “Teshuva” of each Individual human-being (for any “Immoral Choices/s” they have made) which then would “prevent” the materialization of any potentially “negative state” (computed at the previous Neztach’s “UCP’s Computed Potential Object”)! So, we can see, that these “five-essential” HCD’s are (indeed) “centered” around the human capacity to select “Moral/Immoral Choices” based on the “free Moral Choice” (unique) characteristic of human-beings (e.g., unlike any other “inanimate” or “animate”: “plants” or “animals”);

Once again, the UCP’s “motivation” underlying these “five-essential” HCD’s is closely related to the fulfillment of the UCP’s overall “Ultimate Geulah Goal” of steering the entire physical universe towards it “Perfected Geulah State” (e.g., “Morally”, “Spiritually” and even “Physically”)! Since the whole “aim” and “Goal” of the universe’s creation- sustenance- and evolution- by this singular higher-ordered UCP is to evolve the whole universe from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: animals, plants and human-beings to the Ultimate “Geulah Goal” of the whole of Humanity realizing the singularity of this “Universal Computational/Consciousness Reality”, including its unique characteristics of the Dyanmic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” (DEMP), “All-Goodness”, “Peace and Harmony”; therefore those “five-essential HCD’s assist is “steering” Humanity (as a whole – as well as each Individual human-being) towards the attainment of this “Perfected Geulah Goal” State, through our experiencing of the “equivalent positive/negative state/s” produced by our Moral (or “G-d forbid”) Immoral Choice/s, and our ability to make “Teshuva” or to “learn” from those “negative” (“Immoral Choice/s” ensued) or “positive” (“Moral Choice/s produced) Choices! Interestingly, this new NMGCC discovery of “G-D’s Physics” new manner in which the UCP’s actually computes each and every object’s “Gimateria-based” (Hebrew letters’ numerical value – as associated with these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s) is found to differentiate between the manner in which the UCP utilizes these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s – for human-beings (e.g., possessing a “free Moral Choice”) as opposed to the other “Non-Human”, e.g., “inanimate” and “animate”: plants and animals: As noted above, for human beings, the UCP’s utilization of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s is aimed at “teaching” and “perfecting” our Moral nature such that we realize through these five “secondary-essential” HCD’s our “inseparability” from each other as well as from this singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness

Reality” (UCR), which is a part of the overall UCP’s advancement of Humanity (and the universe) towards the fulfillment of its “Ultimate Geulah Perfected Moral & Spiritual State”! Hence, in order to “teach” and “perfect” each and every Individual human-being (and Humanity as a whole) through the operation of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s the UCP utilizes each one of these five “essential-secondary” HCD’s based on each of these five HCD’s “ten zero’s” – as corresponding to the Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD’s)! This implies that in addition to the “basic” Gimatria Consistency Computation (GCC) pertaining to each one of the letters comprising each Individual human-being’s “name” (and the more general GCC of the “general name” of a “human-being”, as discussed above), for each Individual human-being, based on (his or her) “Moral/Immoral Choice/s” (as discussed above) the UCP computes for each one of the 10 zero’s corresponding to each of those five “secondary-essential” the THCD’s complete “Moral rectification”! In contrast, for all “Non-Human” (NH) forms of “inanimate” matter or “animate”: plants and animals, the UCP computes only the GCC based computation of these five “secondary-essential” (as discussed above) based only on the Gimateria (Hebrew letters numerical values associated with each one of these five “secondary-essential” ten zero’s values), i.e., without connection to the THCD’s overall Moral rectification)! One “exception” to this “neutrality” of the THCD’s association with the “ten zero’s” for “Non-Human” (NH) forms (of “inanimate” matter, “animate”: plants and animals) is all instances in which these NH objects are associated (in some form or fashion) to a Moral/Immoral Choice/s that a given Individual human-being has made, in which case it is possible that that NH “object” will be “included” or “affected” by that Individual human-being’s Moral/Immoral Choice/s (e.g., as manifesting through the human DEMP’s associated five “secondary-essential” HCD’s “ten-zero’s”)!

Thus, we see that the manner in which the UCP computes (simultaneously) all exhaustive spatial pixels (and “objects”) in the universe based on a “Non-Material Gimateria Consistency Computation” is “non-material” (in nature)! As we’ve seen previously, due to the “A-Causal Computation” characterization of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm (e.g., stemming from the fact that there cannot exist any direct or indirect “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two or more exhaustive spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF’s frames due to the UCP’s simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for every consecutive UF’s frame/s and the complete “dissolution” of the whole universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s); we’ve realized that since there cannot exist any such (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two (or more exhaustive) spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF’s frames, therefore there cannot be any “transference” or “effects” across any two consecutive UF’s frames: in other words, one UF’s cannot “affect” or “create” any “effect” or “influence” upon its subsequent UF’s frame/s! Instead, we have to look at the singular higher-ordered UCP – not only as the sole and singular “Universal Consciousness Reality” existing both “during” each of its consecutively produced UF’s frame/s, and also solely existing “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s, as the “Computational Invariance Principle” (of “G-D’s Physics New Scientific Paradigm” teaches us; But even beyond that, we realize (in this article) that the manner in which this singular higher-ordered Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle (or Universal Consciousness Reality) computes each and every exhaustive spatial pixel’s object in the universe depends entirely upon this singular UCP’s Gimatria based (Hebrew letters) Consistency Computation, which is “guided” based on the UCP’s or “Universal Consciousness Reality’s (UCR) overall “pre-planned” Blueprint for progressing the entire physical universe from inanimate “matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-being towards the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” in which Humanity and Science will recognize the “Oneness”, “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony” of this singular higher ordered Universal Consciousness Reality! We’ve discovered in this (unique) article that the

manner in which this singular higher-ordered UCR continuously creates-“dissolved”- re-computes- and evolves- every exhaustive spatial-pixel and object in the universe based on this NMGCC computation which differentiates between Human (H) and Non-Human (NH: “inanimate” matter, or “animate”: plants and animals) by incorporating (in addition to the basic Gimateria based computation of every object’s Hebrew name as associated with those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s ten zero’s numerical value etc.) also the DEMP’s manifestation through those five “secondary-essential” HCD’s THCD’s Moral rectification associated with the “ten-respective zero’s”! We thus obtain an entirely new conception of the true nature of the physical universe – which is essentially “non-material”: it is only a

manifestation of the singular higher-ordered UCR (which constitutes the only “constant,” “uniform” and “continuous” reality existing both “during” its production of each consecutive UF’s frames comprising all exhaustive spatial pixels of the universe, as well as existing solely without the presence of any physical universe “in-between” any two such consecutive UF’s frames), which has “pre-planned” the whole origination- sustenance- and evolution- of the entire physical universe from “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the Ultimate “Perfected Geulah Goal” in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this “Universal Consciousness Reality” characterized by “All-Goodness,” “Morality,” “Peace” and “Harmony”!

"UCR's Gimatria-DEP-Geulah Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions" Diagram

The Centrality of “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) in “G-D’s Physics” New Universe!

One of the key differences between the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm and the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm is the “Centrality of Human Consciousness” – i.e., in “space” and “time”, and its intimate connection with the “Universal Consciousness Reality’s” (UCR’s) “Geulah Driven Universe” (GDU)! This is because according to “G-D’s Physics” New (empirically proven) Scientific Paradigm, it seems that “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” (CHCF) plays a major role in the “Universe’s Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE)! As we’ve already seen, there is clear (and direct) empirical evidence for the centrality of this CHCF in terms of its UNCIARE’s acceleration in the universe! As outlined above, in contrast to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (e.g., which has been negated both based on the experimental failure to detect its existence experimentally, and “G-D’s Physics” principle computational negation of its associated Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s SRCS Computational Structure!) – which assumes that this (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept can only account for a “constant-rate” expansion rate of the universe; the New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm points at an increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., “UNCIARE” due to the “Collective Human Consciousness Focus”, which occurs during the Jewish Rosh Hashanah’s (two days’ special) time-interval!

Indeed, it has been proven empirically (above) that it is solely based on this CHCF that the universe’s rate of expansion “increases over time”, e.g., as indicated by the (otherwise unexplained) “Universe’s Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UCAGUARE)!; An even more direct (further) validation of the centrality of the CHCF was called for Astronomers to validate during the upcoming two days’ Jewish Rosh Hashanah – during September 16th& 17th 2023, in which it is predicted that the universe’s rate of expansion will significantly increase (and continue to increase) during the whole ensuing Jewish year), relative to the universe’s measured rate of expansion in the preceding time prior to Sep. 16-17th! Moreover, previously it’s been shown that this same CHCF may be responsible for the Centrality of Human Consciousness – not just in “time” but also in “space”! This relates to the otherwise “unexplained” empirically validated phenomenon wherein the Astronomical

measurement of the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion (UARE) also indicates that planet Earth stands at the center of this UARE! In other words, it may be the case wherein the accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion – i.e., related to “space”, wherein it is only relative to planet Earth’s position that this accelerated rate of expansion pertaining to the furthest regions of space (wherein the farther any galactic element exists relative to planet Earth the faster its measured acceleration would be)! If (for instance) it is found that such equivalent Astronomical measurements of the UARE – do not yield the same “symmetrical increase” in the universe’s UARE then this would validate the centrality of planet Earth (and its associated centrality of this CHCF) – in “space”, as well as in “time”!

“G-D’s Physics” Novel CHCF’s Center of the Universe Hypothesis!

We therefore reach an “astounding” new Hypothesis of “G-D’s Physics”, i.e., hypothesizing that at the center of the universe’s existence, dynamics and development – stand our planet Earth due to this CHCF, including the rotation of our sun (around it) and the accelerated expansion of other galactic elements “emanating” from planet Earth’s CHCF! This is because once we realize that the evolution of the physical universe cannot be explained merely due to an any initially assumed “Big-Bang” nuclear event- e.g., based on the empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm (above); and that (in fact), the basic SRCS Computational Structure of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm was shown to be negated by “G-D’s Physics” (novel) “Computational Duality Principle” (CDP) – i.e., as inevitably leading to both “logical-inconsistency” and (ensuing) “computational indeterminacy” that are both negated by the CDP’s insistence upon the (proven) capacity of this apparently SRCS Computational System to determine the accelerated expansion of the universe – which (according to the CDP) points at the singularity of this singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF’s frame/s)! And most significantly, empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” (above) unique “Critical Prediction” regarding the “Universe’s Non-Continuous Increase in its Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (UNCIARE) – as more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm’s GRT’s assumed “constant rate” of the universe’s expansion rate! Therefore, we must negate (and reject) the Old “Material-Causal” GRT’s Paradigm’s assumption wherein the entire physical universe has been created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event, and that its accelerated rate of expansion can be explained through

negated based on the three abovementioned considerations)!

The alternative (novel) explanation offered by the New (empirically validated) “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm for the origination- sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe is solely based on the operation of the singular (higher-ordered) “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) that (solely) exists both “during” its computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s (as solely responsible for the computation of every exhaustive spatial pixel’s four basic physical features of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”!); And specifically, as associated with this UCP’s connection with the CHCF – which brings about the UCP’s initiation of the UNCIARE (empirically validated) phenomenon! In other words, the UNCIARE empirically validated phenomenon (unequivocally) proves that the origination of the entire physical universe, and its accelerated rate of expansion (e.g., as indicated by the “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion”, CAGUARE) is brought about by the UCP’s consecutive computation of every consecutive UF’s frame/s – and specifically by the CHCF’s UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, e.g., assumed to take place at every Annual “Jewish Rosh-Hashanah” two days’ time-interval (i.e., this year this will take place during Sep. 16-17th 2023 and onwards in which it is predicted the rate of the universe’s expansion will increase significantly, relative to the rate of the universe’s expansion prior to the 16-17th – which I’ve called Astronomers and Cosmologists to test experimentally!) Indeed, once we realize that the entire physical universe “dissolves” back into the singularity of the UCP “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s and that there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing in any single- or multiple- UF’s frame/s; and therefore that the only “force” that creates- “dissolves”- re-creates- and evolves- any exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe is this singular higher-ordered UCP; hence, based on the clear empirical evidence indicating an UNCIARE increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion associated with the CHCF (hypothesized to take place during the Jew Rosh Hashanah!) we reach the inevitable theoretical conclusion wherein the expansion of the entire physical universe depends upon the CHCF – which brings about this UNCIARE increase in the universe’s expansion rate (beginning in each Jewish Rosh Hashanah and continuing throughout the entire subsequent Jewish Year).

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion wherein taking together these two empirically validated facts:

a) Empirical Validation of “G-D’s Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, which according to G-D’s Physics is associated with the CHCF (e.g., specifically during the Jewish “Rosh-Hashanah” special two days’ time interval, as noted above: a call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test this UNCIARE-JRH during the upcoming Sep. 16th-17th, 2023 & onwards!) In other words, this UNCIARE (JRH) empirically confirmed phenomenon points at the centrality of CHCF “in time”, i.e., specifically during the JRH (e.g., to be directly confirmed through the above call for Astronomers/Cosmologists to test during the upcoming JRH!)

b) Centrality of Earth’s CHCF for the Universe’s Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! The empirically observed “unexplained” “Cosmological-Astronomical Gap in the Universe’s Accelerated Rate of Expansion” (CAGUARE) (indicates that the rate of the universe’s expansion has increased (significantly) from its early “Background Radiation” stage to the current (increased) rate in the universe’s expansion!)? This phenomenon is associated with Planet Earth’s “Epicenter” of the universe – in “space” (e.g., based on the fact that the accelerated rate of the our regions of the universe is proportional to the distance from “Earth”)!)

Taken together, these empirically validated (major otherwise “unexplained”) phenomena point at the centrality of Earth’s “Collective Human Consciousness Focus” – in “space” and “time”: as the (functional)

center of the universe! It also reinforces the singularity of the higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” as the sole source “originating” the entire physical universe (at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36^{50}$ (sec)!”)

Indeed, over and beyond the abovementioned empirical validations of “G-D’s Physics” two unique “Critical Predictions”, e.g., associated with the “UNCIARE” and “Proton-Radius Puzzle” findings, the two above empirical findings, i.e., regarding: a) Empirical Validation of “G-D’s Physics” UNCIARE (annual) increase in the rate of the universe’s expansion, which according to G-D’s Physics is associated with the CHCF; b) Centrality of Earth’s CHCF for the Universe’s Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion! clearly point at the Earth’s CHCF’s associated “Epicenter of the Universe” – i.e., both in “time” & “space”! Once again, if we wish to further validate in an even more direct manner the centrality of “Earth’s Epicenter of the Universe” (EEU) related to its CHCF (EEU-CHCF), then Astronomers are invited to test two additional unique “Critical Predictions” of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm:

1) UNCIARE-JRH: as noted (above), an even more direct empirical validation of “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” New Scientific Paradigm, relates to a further testing of its additional “Critical Prediction” regarding the UNCIARE at the (upcoming) JRH (Sep. 16-17th 2023) in which it is predicted that the rate of the universe’s expansion will increase during these two days (and continue constantly throughout the next Jewish Year, relative to the rate of the universe’s expansion rate prior to Sep. 16-17th)!

2) EEU Validation: “Non-Earth’s Non-Epicenter Measurements” (NEN-EM)! An additional (even more direct) testing of the Centrality of Earth’s CHCF for the Universe’s Observed Accelerated Rate of Expansion would be an empirical validation of a measurement of the universe’s “non-harmonious”, i.e., “non-equivalent” accelerated expansion rate – of the farthest regions of the universe, when measured at a location “distant” from Earth (e.g., such as for instance from “Mars” or other “distant” Non-Earth location)! This is because, if indeed, any such measurement of the universe’s accelerated rate of expansion (of a greater rate of expansion proportional to the distance from Earth’s measurement) would be found to be “un-equivalent” (in all directions – for all furthest regions of the universe), as opposed to the accelerated (“equivalent” or “harmonious”) rate of the universe’s expansion as measured from “Earth’s Universe’s Epi-center” (EEU), then this would indicate that indeed Earth’s (CHCF) Epicenter is in fact that the (functional) center of the entire physical universe!

In order to be able to accept this new (profound) metamorphosis of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm underlying both GRT & QM, which assume that the universe was created (or “caused”) by an initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event (and is expanding due to a purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept which could not be verified experimentally and which is negated by the New empirically validated “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm, it is necessary to “retrace” the emergence of the basic “Paradigmatic-Crisis”, e.g., signifying this Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm: indicated by the fundamental “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM, and its principle inability to explain the empirically observed accelerated rate of the universe’s expansion – assumed to be “caused” by the (purely hypothetical) “dark-matter” concept (assumed to comprise up to 95% of all the mass in the universe, but which could not be verified experimentally despite numerous attempts to do so over the past two full decades!)) As we’ve seen, such a (fundamental) “Paradigmatic-Crisis” characterizes (according to Thomas Kuhn’s 1962 famous analysis of the “Structure of Scientific Revolutions”) the need for an ensuing “Paradigmatic-Shift” from this Old “Material-Causal” New “G-D’s Physics” (CUFT) Scientific Paradigm! Indeed, the acceptance of the New “A-Causal Computation” “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm is dependent upon the fulfillment of few (stringent) criteria including: a) Capacity of the New “G-D’s Physics” Scientific Paradigm to resolve the (apparent) GRT-QM “theoretical inconsistency”

(which has been shown previously stemming from the discovery of the singular higher-ordered UCP which simultaneously computes all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features – at the incredible rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 50 \text{ sec}!$ ” thereby producing an extremely rapid series of “Universal Frames” comprising the entire physical universe at every “minimal time-point”!) b) Offering an alternative (satisfactory) explanation for the universe's accelerated rate of expansion – based on the UNCIARE's associated CHCF (outlined above); c) Identification- and empirical validation- of at least one unique “Critical Prediction/s” of “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm as more valid than the corresponding predictions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's GRT's & QM's predictions! (Indeed, the abovementioned empirical validations of two such unique “Critical Predictions” related to UNCIARE and the “Proton Radius Puzzle” findings indicate that “G-D's Physics” New Scientific Paradigm is more valid than the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's GRT and QM's corresponding predictions)!

Hence, based upon the fulfillment of these (stringent) necessary conditions for the acceptance of “G-D's Physics” (CUFT) – points at “G-D's Physics” as the New (valid) Scientific Paradigm for the Twenty-First Century! It is important to note that this New “G-D's Physics” was shown to resolve the apparent “theoretical-inconsistency” between GRT & QM – and in fact unify between them based on its discovery of the (novel) “Universal Computational Formula”, which was also shown to unify (for the first time in Theoretical Physics) between the Four Basic Physical Features (of “space”, “energy”, “mass” and “time”), as well as between the Four Forces! Nevertheless, the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm was characterized as an “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, stemming from its discovery of the singular (higher-ordered) UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF's frames (back into the singularity of the UCP)! According to this New “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm, there cannot exist any (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical interactions between any (two or more) exhaustive spatial pixels existing either in the same- or different- UF's frame/s! This profound new discovery made by the New “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm principally negates some of the most basic assumptions of the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm, including: GRT's “Big-Bang Model” and the existence of any purely hypothetical “dark-matter” concept (as the assumed “caused” for the accelerated expansion of the physical universe, as explained above).

Instead, “G-D's Physics” New “A-Causal Computation” (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm points at the fact that the whole origination-sustenance- “dissolution”- and development- of every exhaustive spatial pixel in the universe (as well as its entirety) has been “pre-planned” by this singular higher-ordered UCP to evolve the universe from its initial “inanimate matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State” in which Humanity and Science will recognize the singularity of this “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle” (UCP) or “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR), which is also characterized by Humanity's (and Science's) “embracing” of this singular UCP's/UCR's intrinsic properties of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” & “Harmony”! Thus, the New (empirically validated) “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm explains the whole origination- sustenance- (“dissolution”-) and development- of the entire physical universe: not as created by an initial “random” “Big-Bang” nuclear event, and the whole development of the universe – as leading to an (“inevitable”) “dissipation” (e.g., based on the Second Law of Thermodynamics), which was shown to be negated by “G-D's Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Paradigm and its CDP; but rather as being “pre-planned” by this singular higher-ordered UCP/UCR for the fulfillment of the universe's “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State” (e.g., Morally, Spiritually and even Physical-

ly)! In that sense, the (above) empirical validation of “G-D's Physics” two (unique) “Critical Predictions”

“G-D's Physics” Unifies All Physical, Biological, Moral and Spiritual Facets of Human- & Universal- Development!

In this sense, the New “G-D's Physics” Scientific Paradigm completely unifies between the various facets, i.e., Physical, Biological, Moral and even Spiritual of the universe's and of Humanity! Once we realize that there cannot exist any (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” physical relationship/s between any two (or more) exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (e.g. existing either in the “same- or “different” UF's frame/s), and that therefore there cannot also exist any “material-causal” relationship/s or even “effects” existing across any two different (consecutive) UF's frame/s, we begin realizing that the only manner in which Theoretical Physics can explain (or describe) the “origination”, “sustenance” or “development” of the universe (or of any “subsystem” found within it) – is solely based upon the singular higher-ordered “Universal Computational/Consciousness Principle”(UCP) or “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR) which solely exists both “during” each consecutive UF's frame (e.g., as simultaneously computing all exhaustive spatial pixels' four basic physical features), as well as singularly exists “in-between” any two consecutive UF's frame/s (e.g., during which time the whole physical universe “dissolves” back into the singularity of this UCR)! We realize that (based upon the “Computational Invariance Principle” and associated “Universal Consciousness Reality” theoretical postulates) there truly exists only one singular higher-ordered UCR which manifests as the entirety of the physical universe “during” each consecutive UF's frame/s, but remains without the presence of any physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF's frame/s!

We therefore reach the inevitable conclusion that the existence of the entire physical universe merely represents a “transient” and “phenomenal” manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR, e.g., existing only “during” each consecutive UF's frame/s but “dissolving” back into the singularity of the UCP/UCR! Hence, the continuous “origination”, “dissolution” (“in-between” any two consecutive UF's frame/s of the entire universe back into the UCR), “development” and “Ultimate Goal” of the entire physical universe is only geared at fulfilling this UCR's “Ultimate Geulah Goal” Objective which is to “steer” the universe from its initial “inanimate matter” through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings towards the realization of the singularity of this UCR by Humanity (and Science), which would lead to the “Perfected Geulah Goal State” of Humanity (and the universe) in which Humanity lives in accordance with this singular UCR's “sublime” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” & “Harmony”! No longer, therefore, can we “hold on” to the Old “Material-Causal” Paradigm's basic assumption wherein both the origination of the universe by an assumed “random” “Big-Bang” nuclear event, as well as the origination of all Biological Species assumed to be “caused” by a “random” “material-causal” physical interactions between (certain) “genetically mutated – environmentally-compatible” specific organism/s and “challenging Environmental Conditions” (as opposed to other “un-mutated” organisms) which “caused” only those “genetically mutated – environmentally compatible” organism/s to “survive” and pass on their genetic information to subsequent generations?! This is because (once again), first of all there could not have been any such (direct or even indirect) “material-causal” physical interaction/s either between the (initially assumed) “Big-Bang” nuclear event and the creation of any suns, galaxies, matter or energy etc. (e.g., in the “first”, “second”, “third” ... “trillionth” etc. UF's frame – due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels in the universe (for every consecutive UF's frame/s and the complete “dissolution” of the whole universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF's frame/s); nor between those assumed “genetically mutated” organism/s and their “challenging Environmental Conditions” (e.g., at any single- or multiple- UF's frame/s) once again due to the UCP's simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels (for every consecutive UF's frame/s) and the complete “dissolution” of the entire physical

universe “in—between” any two such consecutive UF’s frame/s! Secondly, we realize that the whole development of the entire physical universe – from its initial “inanimate matter” through “animate”: plants, animals, human-beings must be “organized” and “directed” based on the UCP’s Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD’s) which fulfill the UCP’s/UCR’s Ultimate Geulah-Goal Directed (GGD) Universe!

So, we obtain an entirely different conception of the whole origination-sustenance- “dissolution”- and development of the whole universe as “motivated” and “driven” by the singular higher-ordered UCR’s “steering” of the universe towards the “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State”! In that sense, the various facets of the universe’s development – Physical, Biological, Moral and even Spiritual are all seen to be completely “integrated” as part and parcel of this “overarching”, “preplanned” “Blueprint Plan” of the UCP to advance the universe from its initial “inanimate” matter through “animate”: plants, animals and human-beings ultimately leading to Humanity’s (and Science’s) recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR and its associated “sublime” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” & “Harmony”, constituting the fulfillment of the universe’s “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State”! Moreover, we (excitedly) realize that with the current article’s acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm Science (and Humanity, more generally) are “entering” this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal State” of the universe, in which the singularity of this UCR is recognized and accepted by Science, and accordingly Humanity begins living in accordance with this singular higher-ordered “sublime” characteristics of “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”!

“G-D’s Physics” New Perfected “Geulah” Directed Universe!

We therefore reach an entirely new conception of the origin- true nature-sustenance- and development- of the whole physical universe, and our special role, as Individual human-being (possessing a “Free-Moral Choice”) within it! We realize that the universe was not created (or “caused”) by an (“random”) initial “Big-Bang” nuclear event, nor can its accelerated rate of expansion be explained by any (purely hypothetical, non-existent!) “Dark-Matter” concept; nor the development of all Biological forms can be explained by DNSP “Material-Causal” assumption which was strictly negated by “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” New empirically validated Scientific Paradigm! We’ve seen that according to this New “G-D’s Physics” “A-Causal Computation” Scientific Paradigm there cannot exist any “material-causal” physical interactions between any two (or more) spatial pixels existing in the same- or different- UF’s frame/s; Moreover, based on the two (profound) theoretical postulates of the “Computational Invariance Principle” and associated “Universal Consciousness Reality” we’ve realized that truly, there exists only the singular higher-ordered “Universal Consciousness Reality” (UCR/UCP) which exists both “during” each consecutive UF’s frame/s and also solely exists “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s (without the presence of any physical universe)! Hence, we realized that the only manner in which we can explain (and understand) the origination- (“dissolution”) sustenance- and development- of the entire physical universe (as well as of any exhaustive spatial pixel within it) is solely based on the analysis of this singular higher-ordered UCR’s Ten Hierarchical Computational Dimensions (THCD’s), and associated THCD’s-Universal Computational Formula (UCF), which essentially “steer” the universe from its initial “inanimate” matter (form) through “animate”: plants, animals, and human-beings – all preplanned to lead to the Ultimate Perfected “Geulah Goal State” of the entire universe, in which Humanity (and Science) will recognize the singularity of this UCR, alongside its “sublime” characteristics “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, e.g., and lead a life compatible with these UCR’s characteristics!

The amazing discovery (then) made by this New “G-D’s Physics” Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm is that not only the universe does not operate merely through (direct or indirect) “material-causal” physical in-

teraction/s (e.g., at the relativistic or quantum levels); cannot be regarded as a “solid”, “constant” or “continuous” phenomenon – but is rather being continuously “computed”- “dissolved”- “re-created” and “developed” by the singular higher-ordered UCR/UCP (at the unfathomable rate of “ $c^2/h = 1.36 \cdot 10^{50} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ ”) as an extremely rapid series of UF’s frames (comprising the entire physical universe at every such “minimal time-point”); And is in fact, only a manifestation of this singular higher-ordered UCR – which exists both “during” its simultaneous computation of all exhaustive spatial pixels for each consecutive UF’s frame/s, and also solely exists (without the presence of any physical universe) “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s! The amazing discovery made by “G-D’s Physics” New Twenty-First Century (empirically validated) Scientific Paradigm is that this singular higher-ordered UCR Reality, which manifests as the physical universe (during each consecutive UF’s frame/s, and solely exists without the presence of the entire physical universe “in-between” any two consecutive UF’s frame/s) continuously “steers” the universe towards its “Ultimate Perfected Geulah Goal” State, and is in fact continuously computing for each exhaustive spatial pixel based on the abovementioned “Gimatria” based and “Dynamic-Equilibrium Moral Principle” – which are all computed in order to attain this “Ultimate Perfected Geulah State” of Humanity and the Universe! Another amazing aspect of the current acceptance of the New “G-D’s Physics” as the new (valid) Twenty-First Century Scientific Paradigm is the realization that in fact Science and Humanity are entering this “Ultimate Geulah Goal Perfected State”, with the acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” as the New 21st Century Scientific Paradigm! This is because at the “center” of the acceptance of “G-D’s Physics” New Scientific Paradigm is its recognition of the singularity of the UCR/UCP as the sole and singular reality underlying (and indeed “transcending”) the physical universe, and its recognition of this singular higher-ordered UCR as being characterized by those “sublime” characteristics of “All-Goodness”, “Morality”, “Peace” and “Harmony”, and the need for Humanity to lead a life in accordance with these “sublime” characteristics of this singular UCR Reality, i.e., signifying that “Perfected Geulah Goal State” of Humanity and the universe!

Dedication

This special article is dedicated to the Lubavitcher Rabbi whose vision is to bring Humanity towards its Perfected Geulah State (including the observance of the “Seven Noahide Laws”) and in memory of the greatness of three other Leaders of the Jewish People, King David and the Baal Shem Tov, and Maimonides (who all advanced the Jewish People and the whole world towards this Ultimate Perfected Geulah State of Humanity and the World)!

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